

Western Blots related to manuscript:

Oct4 is a gatekeeper of epithelial identity by regulating cytoskeletal organization in skin keratinocytes

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Related to Figure 1C

Related to Figure 1F

UT

pcDNAEGFP

pcDNAOCT4

pcDNAOCT4EGFP

Oct4

GFP

Oct4

Oct4

GAPDH

GAPDH

GAPDH

GAPDH

Related to Figure 5D

GAPDH

β -actin

E-cadherin

β -catenin

ZO1

Related to Figure 7B

pCEP-Oct4-WT

Oct4

GAPDH

pCEP-Oct4-AA

Oct4

GAPDH

pCEP-Oct4-EE

Oct4

GAPDH

Related to Figure S1D

